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Situating Traditional Angami Women Through Their Folksongs

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Abstract:

Oral traditional existence of the Angami tribe prevailed in the pre colonial times, prior to the introduction of the written script during the colonial period, which ushered in a new and modern way of life. Such were times when modern feminism was not only unknown but irrelevant, where the labour of men and women complemented each other, their main preoccupation being to survive together. In an interesting way, we find women freely expressing their feelings, thoughts, individual opinions, and opposing viewpoints in Angami Folksongs. It is not surprising, when all things are considered, especially the casteless, egalitarian, democratic nature of the community, that there are many Angami folksongs that focus on women and their existence which is, at once, prosaic and poetic, matter-of-fact and soulful.

Keywords: Angami women, Oral tradition, Folksongs, Democratic tribe.

Introduction

Angami is one of many tribes that make up the Naga people in the northeast region of India. Pristine ancestral Angami existence can be found in the timeless pre-colonial world of

oral tradition, before the influence of modernized way of life which was introduced during the colonial period crept in. It was in 1831-32 that the British colonials first set foot in the Naga inhabited region, when a troop led by Captain Jenkins, Pemberton, and Gordon were deputed to explore a route between Manipur and the plains of Assam, through the Angami area and met with fierce resistance (Butler 296). The final breakdown of native resistance in 1880, marked the British colonial rule in Naga territory. It remains to be said that if colonial influence soon changed much of the traditional pattern of life, its officials and western researchers recorded much of the ancestral Naga oral traditional way of life, such as J.H. Hutton, J.P. Mills, Verrier Elwin, R.B. Pemberton, John Butler, R.G. Woodthorpe, A.W. Davis, Mary Clark, Christoph Von Fürer-Haimendorf, to name a few.

During the ancestral times, the Angami community found subsistence in agriculture, and as hunter-gatherers. The patriarchal community being a warrior tribe, menfolk fiercely defended life and property, and hunting is a way of life. Engaged with other activities which are mostly outdoor activities, their womenfolk support them by taking charge of the domestic front. Such were times when modern feminism was not only unknown but irrelevant, where the labour of men and women complimented each other, their main preoccupation being to survive together. What mattered most is the birth of children, male or female. This is indicated in the pronouncement of blessings in such times as marriages, founding village settlements, feasts of merit and other special occasions, as documented in *Life in Khonoma*: “They will multiply like crabs and spiders./ They will live long” (152).

Growing up, both girls and boys hobnob with their respective age-group members, and sleep in their respective dormitories called *kichüki*. It is there that they learned life lessons and folksongs alongside their respective duties, boys tending toward guarding the community, while girls learned to weave. Occasionally, boys and girls labour together in the fields with their peer-group members known as *Pelimia*, especially for rice paddy cultivation

which is their staple food grain, while all along singing together. In fact, folksongs are a part and parcel of their existence from birth to death, which brought not only joy, comfort, but gave impetus and vigor to physical labour, embolden them for courage, ease the tedium of monotony, and release emotions of all hues. Kramer points out that Lomax was confident that his cybernetic approach to song style produced compelling results, not just about the dissemination of songs across the world, but also about the functional factors within particular societies and roughly predict the basic structure of a culture by a Cantometric profile of its singing style, that Yahraes in his “Music as a Measure of Psychological and Cultural Development” tells of how Lomax thought it might even soon be possible to listen to a few recorded songs from an unidentified geographical area to be able to identify the area and describe in general terms such characteristics as the culture’s predominant means of livelihood, its political organization, its attitude towards sex, and its child-rearing philosophy (Kramer). As such, Angami Folksongs embed significant cultural and societal normative behavior and beliefs. This study will situate Angami women as reflected in the poetic expressions of their folksongs.

Oral Angami folksongs

Woodthorpe, in his observation, states: “Angamis struck us as a very cheerful, frank, hospitable, brave race, and for hill people wonderfully clean”, that they would see the men of the village in long unbroken line descending, bringing rice, wood etc., and shouting in wonderful unison their peculiar cry which accompany labour, of voices swelling which is “almost music” (55). This “almost music” is part of their chant-like song called “Kehu” which is a community song, of repetitive vocables in multiple parts of low and high notes, alternately and repeatedly, which creates a reverberating effect (Peseyie 114).

Dorson points out that folksongs were the first cultural indicator that Alan Lomax had examined in his *Folk Song Style and Culture*, because world-wide recordings of folksongs were available: “peoples in all cultures sang folksongs and, by their built-in redundancies [repetitiveness], folksongs mirrored cultures. Folktales, being less redundant, could stray further from cultural norms” (39).

Angami folktales, as with oral tradition, are prone to variations and changes for being subjected to retelling by individuals through word of mouth, handed down from generation to generation. However, with their folksongs such exigencies of change are significantly avoided as traditional Angami folk tunes strictly consist of 9-syllabic lines. This is also the reason why the song lyrics can be fitted to different set tunes called *Lige*, appropriate to the occasion (Tseikhanuo). For instance, the lyrics of romantic love song can be fitted to fieldwork songs or cow-herding songs in the forest, which have their own suitable tunes. The 9-syllabic lines not only make folksongs adaptable to various tunes, but also give accuracy of lyrics to a large extent, rendering them less prone to changes and more authenticity, unlike other oral accounts.

The anonymous folksongs taken up to look into the position of traditional Angami women, appear in the book, *üca-53*, compiled by Shürhozelie, which consists of 53 traditional and modern compositions. The term, *üca*, literally means song lyrics. This book is used as a text in schools for Tenyidie students. Tenyidie is the language of the Tenyimia people which is a broader umbrella group of tribes including angami tribe, and Tenyidie and Angami are interchangeably used. Writing about this group, Woodthorpe differentiates them to be the “so-called Angamis, eastern and western”, to be the kilted tribes, as opposed to the other non-kilted Naga tribes, noting that “in nothing is the difference so marked as in the waist cloth” (49).

The girl-child in the Traditional Angami Community

That the girl child in the Angami community has a happy childhood, is seen in the way women reminisce about the simple joys just being under parental care, as reflected in their folksongs. The life of Adolescents and youthful members, growing up with peer-group friends, learning together informally in their dormitories or *kichüki*, working and socializing together with boys and girls of their own age-groups, which made labour fun as well, can be gleaned from their folksongs. In “*Chahechü*” which can be translated as “Wayside Shed”, we hear the voice of a girl who is so happy with the age-group friends that she does not miss home as such. That the group is still far from home is suggested by the fact that they are resting in one of the wayside shed, which can be normally found along the pathways as wayside shelters even today. However, even during such happy times, danger looms near and the lonely voice suddenly cries out, “*A rülihüü suonie a sie ki/ Mepfü keruo khakelie nyi ga?*” (27). The lines can be translated as, “I, an only child, who will stand behind/ Crying the war cry, defend?” She finds herself in a vulnerable position when unknown enemies suddenly attack and she has no one to protect her, as brothers rush to defend their own sisters. If a female is seen as being helpless, it is not for any discriminatory mindset, but because of the real danger of being actually killed by a physically more muscular and agile enemy warrior.

As with other Naga tribes, Angami community is flexible and there is no social segregation of genders. Boys and girls, men and women, mix freely, socializing for work and leisure, singing and laughing in fellowship. This does not mean that there are no activities which are restricted and considered strictly confined to males or females. There are certain events, like, gate-pulling ceremony that involves rites and rituals, which only men are allowed to participate in, just as loom-weaving is accomplished by women and is taboo for men to touch the weaving tools.

The Angami girl-child, through adolescence and youthful stage, on the whole, leads a happy life. They are free from the cruel consequences of dowry, child marriage, sati, genital mutilations, which some of their counterparts in certain communities are subjected to. So much so, missing peer-group companions when they get married and responsibilities come as wife and mother, is wistfully sounded in many of their songs. Marriage is always a watershed in a woman's life as it entails, in general, child-bearing, birthing, and nursing. As such, this is more keenly felt in olden days as reflected in the folksong, "Thenu Nie We" (You Woman), where the fading of her beauty, too, in the process, is poignantly seen to be more ephemeral than a flower :

Meniepounuo sei bodi gei ba

Ciethie pou ro thecie puo rhe chü.

Liehuvuo-o thenumia rüli,

Ciethie pa ro thecie puo pie ze

Keta sie sü ra kethotolo. (29)

Translation:

Flower on a sturdy tree

That blooms this year, gives better bloom the following year

As for the lot of a woman

Marriage this year finds her with a child the following year

Verily, she soon fades away.

As such, Butler is to note, with grief and surprise, how Angami women age so soon due to “hard work and exposure, coupled with the trials of early maternity” (303). In “A Kesuoü” (My Badness), a newly wedded wife working in the field all by herself one strong windy day, could hear the sounds of a peer-group, carried over by the rushing wind from a distance. Melancholic, her rambling thoughts take her back to the carefree childhood days:

Nha mezü rho cha meluo nu kha

Zo zhütuo mu hatsa tsurüluo,

Kezha ki we kenienuo pie chü

Kesuo we jü lhou’rü huvuo-o. (19)

Translation:

“Where plant-tips will be lopped and strewn

Come along that path”

Childhood years, when parents would say such

Life was easy, then, without the bad.

The short folksong, “Hie Pieü” (Our Daughter), tells of how, as parents, they would once fuss over their infant daughter, as they take her along with them to work in the fields, “Pekra khrie di se nu pie keyie” / “Sorry to let her cry, cuddled her in turns” (34).

In the folksong “Rütsolhouü”, the woman who was bereft of her parents early in life and mistreated by her uncle, though lonely and beset with difficulties in a far-off village, did not wish to return to her village since peer friends with whom she has grown up with, would already be well-settled. “Larü lho” / “Will not return”, she says with rueful finality (5). This

goes to indicate how impactful peer-group friendship can be, especially for such a woman, for whom losing childhood friends is losing all. It is notable that even the handicapped and the orphans receive “equal treatment” in such age groups (*Life in Khonoma* 120).

Women and Freedom of Expression

Pemberton writes in “A Singular Race of People” that Naga women are allowed unreserved conversations and interactions with “all visitors, whether male or female” (43). Hutton points out how Butler describes the Angami folks as living “a form of the purest democracy which it is difficult to conceive of as existing even for a single day” (143). Angami community is fundamentally casteless, classless. There is no gender segregation and status is a matter of meritorious achievement by singular individuals or as a couple. If a man can raise his status by observing a *Feast of Merit*, as the term implies, it is by giving a feast for the whole community after years of labour and good husbandry. This act of sharing his wealth with the community, earns him certain decorative symbols of merit, including a special house-top design. Individual status is tied up with household pride and community welfare, as seen in the folksong dedicated to the man, “Putsolie”, who is reputed for having fulfilled multiple Feasts of Merit and is a blessing for the Kewhimia people (30). As such, Putsolie and his wife, Tenuo, earned the praise and the respect of their people, and are blessed with, “Chü la pecha Kewhimia ge tso/ Zo balieluo Tenuo Putsolie”, which is to say, “May your lives be lengthened to keep partaking/ with all Kewhimia, Tenuo, Putsolie” (ibid.). That the wife’s due diligence is also acknowledged and celebrated during such auspicious events, is reflected here.

In a notable way, we find women freely expressing their feelings and thoughts, individual opinions and opposing viewpoints in Angami Folksongs. The folksong, “Thanuo”, which means “The Hair”, is about a woman who readily agrees to cut off her hair in order to

enable her man to complete decorating his warrior gear *Kia* which requires hair. It concludes with the woman reprimanding the man because his realization that it was taboo to use the first crop of hair for such a purpose, dawned on him only after her beautiful hair has been cut pointlessly. In her exasperation, she cries out, “ Pfü kenyü ro dichü hie tha du, / Pesuowa di thepfu kemo-o”/ “ If taboo to use, why did you cut off my hair, then / And spoiling it, O thoughtless man! ” (8). Again, the folksong “ Tsienu Tsu le ” (Setting Out Late One Morning), depicts a woman by the village gate, late one morning, looking out expectantly for her lover’s company, when her brother comes along and repudiates her for being still around and not on her way to the field. She freely expresses her mind, telling him that he is unmindful that she is a woman, a sister, and that there is no perfection in this world:

Kerü nu tsie tsieleu thuo nu

Deiü ba rei dzü-o puokhro tse

Vüprio pou mhiso pou keduo,

Pfhenuo mezü dei vo puoyuo thu

Balie mo mu a zuo a ruo hie. (27)

Translation:

A mighty boulder may lord over the river

But water penetrates beneath,

Vüprio (a type of bamboo) do not sprout adjoining eye-nodes

There is no perfect plantain leaf without a tear from base to tip

So Mother, do not be angry for what my brother faults me with.

The folksong, thus, concludes with the woman telling her mother not to scold her like her unmindful brother. Noteworthy is the way she does not cringe under the critical gaze of her brother, or hides behind an excuse, but frankly and even philosophically, makes her thoughts clear without any feelings of guilt.

Of Love and Arranged Marriages

On the whole, the community thrives in an open environment where active social interaction is encouraged, and individuals, too, can choose their own life partners, or have one arranged by family members. However, it can become problematic for women when they are married off to unfamiliar men outside of their village, and they are uprooted to begin a new life in an unfamiliar surrounding. The following folksongs are such samples of marriages in the Angami community which especially dwells on the lot of womenfolk.

“Avu Nei Hu” (our mutual love) tells of lovers separated, the man by his marriage to a bride as arranged by members of his family, while the woman went on to be married off to a man from another village. The song is about how the once youthful couple meets again when the woman comes to visit her parental home during a festive occasion, along with her child. Her former lover holds the child and places a distinct precious necklace around the child’s neck, telling her that should her husband enquire about the necklace, she should say that it is her parental possession. This folksong reflects of how Angami marriages are both arranged as well as a union of free choice by individuals. A would-be love marriage turns nostalgic in this song, when the woman landed up with an arranged marriage belonging to another village.

The following folksong, too, is one such marriage where the bride came to settle in another village. Having adjusted well, she came to be loved and praised by the husband’s kinfolk but met with an untimely tragic death. In this folksong, “Phoutheguo-o”, which is the name of a male protagonist, we find a man who chose a bride from a distant land (10). It is about how

the woman endeared herself to the husband's household, treading their land and living their way of life, but of how she was slain by enemies, leaving the man to seek for revenge. It tells of how he was unable to find solace and constantly relives her memory. This folksong reflects a marriage that worked out for a woman who had to depart from her land of birth to go and live in her husband's village. Such a marriage would have an advantage for the man in times of hostility between his village and his wife's village, as the man would be considered "a neutral", as Woodthorpe is to also note, when he mentions that such a piece of information was narrated by his native guide (56).

Among the folksongs that have survived, there are a number of folksongs that voice the sad, lonesome experiences of married women, especially those married off to other villages and yearning for the land of their births, their families and peer-group friends. Particularly bleak and tumultuous, is the tragic experience and fate of the woman in the folksong "Sopfünüo". The woman, Sopfünüo, finds herself in a friendless situation as she tries to cope up with a new married life in a distant land. She was relentlessly confronted with the animosity of the jealous women of her husband's village, who send her words, by day and by night, to depart and flee. Reluctant to give in to the pressure for the sake of her children, her resistance finally breaks when she was unable to withstand the oppressive force, and she sets off in the night with her infant child. One hears her innermost philosophical thoughts:

Themia lhou-o khrülhou ha tuoi,

Va puo jü rei va puo lhou la'rü,

Zoya mie mu suonie u rheichie

Mia die kesuo rünyü zoyanyi. (7)

Translation:

Human life, like the lunar light

Do not disappear to reappear

So who would wish to hear bitter words

One's precarious lifelong.

Unfortunately, lightning struck her dead as she made her way to her parental home and her helpless child died with her. Their bodies are believed to have turned into stones. The tragic account of Sopfünuo's story, lives on today as a legend. Two elongated stones, a big one and a small one, believed to be that of Sopfünuo and her child, were dragged to her village, Rüsoma, by her clansmen of old, which can still be seen lying there, and considered as sacred. She is held as a virtuous lady who watches over young men and women as they head for the fields.

As seen in "Sopfünuo", the position of an Angami woman becomes precarious, though it may not be as overwhelming as is the case of Sopfünuo, when she is married off to another village for multiple reasons. In the folksong, "Khrieü", the woman named, Khrieü, who is married off to another village, gets practically cut-off from her familiar kith and kin (6). She is unable to make a journey to visit her parental home during the rainy season due to the high waters of the rivers and streams which lie along the way, while during the dry season danger lurks everywhere, as it is usually the time of warfare and enemies encounter each other. When, one fateful day, Khrieü reaches her parents' front yard, she finds the door half-shut signifying the observation of *genna*, which is a ritual that stipulates abstention from work and non-resident visitors were not entertained or spoken to. However, her mother, who all along had been anxious about her long absence, took pity and let her into the house. The folksong goes on to tell of her reluctance to return to her husband's village. The name, Khrieü, itself, which

means “the loved one”, is suggestive of parental affection. Till today, the name “Khrieü” or its variant, “Khrienuo” is a common name for the girl child.

Some common reasons can be found as to why women are given in marriage to other Angami or Tenyimia villages. A good social standing and better means of the groom’s family, is seen as a fair prospect for a daughter’s future as reflected in “Hie Pieü” :

Pfuchazou-o tuo kevi rüna

Mia sei mia tsie mia ca-o vüwhü

Ba üyie mu hie pieü penyhü” (34)

Which goes,

Pfuchazou village is good to dwell in

The family’s trees and rocks in abundance

The narration goes on to say that such was communicated, and so their beloved daughter was given in marriage. Another reason for women marrying outside their own village, is indicated to be due to the lack of any forthcoming proposals from men of the same village, as in “Lhenu Khokhrieü” (The One Never Wished to Part With), where the soon-to-be- bride regretfully tells her companions who were sorry to let her go and set up home in another village: “Hie kho chüpfü sie kepa nhienu / Kha tha derei hie we la moluo” which means, “Only on the day I take up my basket to leave /Am I urged to remain, too late” (31).

It is noteworthy that a peer-group usually consists of, among others, immediate family members and many clan members with whom marriage is forbidden, as indicated in “Chahechü”, where all of a sudden the peer-group is attacked, and the brotherless girl is distressed as the males’ first responsibility is to protect their own immediate sisters. In such a

scenario, it is not surprising that in the Angami community, there are many arranged marriages within and outside of the village too. Davis notes of how Angami people have exogamous subdivisions, and a man is therefore obliged to look for his wife among the women of one outside of his own, that marriages are, as such, “usually not love matches, atleast as far as the girl is concerned” (306).

Women in Lamentation

In “Phousanyi-o” (One Purification Festival), a mother is seen grieving the loss of her son, all over again, as she watches the rejoicing young men return to the village after fulfilling the sacred bath in the stream during a purification festival (25). The bereft mother yearns to find her son among the happy throng of menfolk in procession, winding up their way to the *tsiepfhe*, which is an elevated meeting place, still found in Angami villages. The memory of her son goes back to his infancy, when she would strap him around her chest with a long piece of woven cloth, caressing him and musing who should care for him when she goes to the field. Her mourning intensifies as she envisions him as an adult, wearing adult armllets, which is a stage when familial bonds become even stronger: “Nie chũthuo nyũ zowhe the nie kha / Kelie zenu jute le sieu” (25). Angami mourners are wont to speak over the dead bodies of their loved ones. Here, the intensity of the mother’s grief is awakened afresh, and she addresses her departed son, as to why he had to leave when he had begun to wear adult armllets and ritual leaf around his wrist, which signifies her regret for the loss of those bonding years.

In like manner, there are many folksongs that raise up images and representations of women mourning the tragic loss of a warrior son, lover, brother, husband. In “Nie Pie Penuo” (Birthing Your Child), we hear the lamentation of a newly married woman who shrouds her slain husband with her favourite cherished dark shawl, mourning, “Avu nou we kru tsu

kenourhe / Kelie zenu a kho le sieu” (9). Which translates, “Now when our hearts flow to unite as one / would you depart from me, love ?”. Again, in “Metsü Kezei” (Rainy Season), there is the wife’s lament over the untimely death of her famed warrior, leaving her with tumultuous thoughts:

Hie nieunuo kegeimia sünuo

Thuo di-o phi mho di-o pema

Zo pie zhü di hie neiu sü gei. (44)

Which goes,

Who were the slayers of my loved one?

What predictions, what dreams dreamt

Preceded the fate of my loved one?

Angami ancestral folks made predictions by certain ritualistic acts, and dreams were consulted before decisive actions were undertaken. Here, the sorrowful woman is left wondering about such things because it would take nothing short of the exceptional, to cause the great fall of such a renowned warrior that her husband had been.

Conclusion

To situate Angami women, as to their position within their community, the stable 9-syllabic Angami folksongs can reflect a traditional democratic way of life where women were free from menacing traditional practices imposed on certain other women in different parts of the world. Carefree childhood of the girl child under parental care; despite the work-filled days, memories of their happy adolescent and youthful years with peer-group companions, were undeniably represented in their songs. Gender segregation or Purdah-like measures,

have no place in such a community that steadfastly promotes active interaction among members for social cohesiveness. Boys and girls grow up among their peer groups, men and women work in the fields together, and the whole community celebrate their festivals by keeping track of the agricultural cycles of the seasons. Women can choose their own husbands, but marriage to someone outside of one's village, can be very lonely, even tragic, as expressed in many songs. Women give due diligence to their domestic workload assigned to them, knowing their menfolk put their lives in the forefront as protectors, which their lamentations indicate. It is not surprising that there are many Angami folksongs that give focus on their women, echoing their thoughts, emotions, and sentiments, which also reflect the democratic nature of the Angami tribe, which are both prosaic and poetic, matter-of-fact and soulful.

It remains to be said, that with the end of the ancestral pre-colonial era and the emergence of a modern and global way of life in the colonial and post colonial times, the dynamics of gender relationships have changed. In the pre-colonial times, decisions needed to be taken would be mostly about warfare and safety measures for survival of the community, and divorce among the Angami folks was uncommon. Today, many men and women, both in the urban and rural areas, are both making a living as professionals in careers, entrepreneurs, and in the unorganized agricultural sector. While more and more women are engaged in activities outside of their homes, men are slower in catching up with the activities at the home front. A research on Angami women shows that “the fathers are not involved much in the lives of their children” (Hibo 30). There is the necessity for a detailed survey to get a better understanding of the status of Naga women in general, and of Angami women in particular, but cases such as infanticide, dowry, bride burning, gang rapes are unknown (Mezhur). Women do not have much voice in decision-making outside of familial matters, and customary laws pertaining to divorce are seen to be too simplistic and male-centric, which are

avenues for further studies to bring more clarity on aspects of continuity and change. Not surprisingly, patriarchal bias and gender hegemony are being voiced today in the fictional and poetic works of native Angami writers, like Easterine Kire, among others. Researchers need to focus and be mindful of Indigenous Feminist approaches which are diverse, complex, and community-specific, and different from Western evaluation methods and paradigms, as pointed out by Meissner et al. The approach adopted by some Angami women to develop leadership among them was stated to be “collaborative not confrontational”, and Pereira argues that women living in contexts where they are blocked from occupying public leadership, can still succeed in developing their leadership abilities if they use strategies that are culturally appropriate and contextually expedient (111). Meanwhile, the debate goes on as to the exact status of Angami women in the 21st Century. Complementary roles that men and women have played in the bygone ancestral times, as a model with flexibility in the details, is food for thought.

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